

BLUE BLOCKS MICRO RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Case Study 2: Innovation and Resilience in Adolescent Learners

WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-01	Date completed 30-3-2026
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A note before you begin

This sheet is for your honest thinking, not a polished account. There are no correct answers. We are not grading your satellite project or your writing. We are interested in how you actually experienced the process: what you thought, what broke, and what you did next.

Write in whatever way feels natural. Short sentences are fine. You can use bullet points if that helps. The only rule is: write what is true, not what sounds good. If the spaces aren't enough, please use a star mark and write it at the bottom or in an extra sheet.

Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

We were trying to learn a lot more in depth about how a satellite is built, and trying to build one myself and try to learn more about rocket science

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

because this project was one of the projects we as students could be capable of achieving and

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

At first I was quite confused because we had no idea of how to build a satellite, it felt like we could not be able to build it

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PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

When our rocket launch failed we were quite upset, disappointed that we would not get our data and we would have to do everything all over again

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

That our cubesat would deploy but not at the right orbit height

2c. What did you do first?

Double check that what happened was true. Check with everyone possible (verify the situation)

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

not ready —

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

We would try to develop the satellite further, try to add some a high resolution camera, try to get more hands on experience

3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

"When something broke or failed, it told me that..."

We were getting there slowly but steadily, one issue at a time

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

I expect everything to go wrong at first, but it all comes together at the end

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

When you are hard working on something, you have to expect failures because a failures are a part of success, not an enemy

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

Thank you.

Please bring this sheet with you on Monday. You will have a chance to use what you wrote in the group challenge and the team presentation. Do not worry about making it neat. The thinking matters, not the handwriting.

Blue Blocks Micro Research Institute, Hyderabad | March 2026 | Case Study 2 of 5

WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-02	Date completed 27/3/26
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A note before you begin

This sheet is for your honest thinking, not a polished account. There are no correct answers. We are not grading your satellite project or your writing. We are interested in how you actually experienced the process: what you thought, what broke, and what you did next.

Write in whatever way feels natural. Short sentences are fine. You can use bullet points if that helps. The only rule is: write what is true, not what sounds good. If the spaces aren't enough, please use a star mark and write it at the bottom or in an extra sheet.

Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

I personally thought we were going to build something that not only helps people but also helps nature and the earth to thrive.

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

To stop what is happening to the earth (global warming) and create a better, brighter future for all of us and for the earth and nature.

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

It felt like we were about to take up a huge project (like climbing Mount Everest) and it is like a whole new journey for us

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

I was just working on the satellite and I then realised that I didn't even know what the sensors are for and what are they called.

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

That I should pay more attention and try to understand it.

2c. What did you do first?

I asked the teachers and they helped me know more about the sensors.

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

I felt as if I would not be able to understand the sensors, but with the teachers' help, I could understand it.

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

I would first think of how can it serve not only humanity but also nature and the earth.
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3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

"When something broke or failed, it told me that..."

I should not quit but keep trying until it succeeds.

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

Even though things will go wrong, that does not mean we should stop trying and just quit, but we should take it as an opportunity to learn something new.

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

I would say — first it may be hard and seem almost impossible but if you change your perspective of how difficult it is — you may unlock a new skill or talent or thought-process that you never thought you could have.

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

Thank you.

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WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-03	Date completed 30/3/26
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Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

Trying to build a cube sat and finding out how rocket science works.

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

the part where our work would go to space

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

At the start I felt like it was not possible because we were just 12 year olds but then I realised that

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

when the rocket countered a anomaly I thought our satellite couldn't deploy.

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

I felt sad

2c. What did you do first?

Ask what went wrong

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

What are the differences

3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

"When something broke or failed, it told me that..."

When something broke or failed I felt sad but I tried again

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

I have no negative thoughts but I feel nervous

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

never give up anything is possible

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

Thank you.

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WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-04	Date completed
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A note before you begin

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Write in whatever way feels natural. Short sentences are fine. You can use bullet points if that helps. The only rule is: write what is true, not what sounds good. If the spaces aren't enough, please use a star mark and write it at the bottom or in an extra sheet.

Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

We were trying to build a cubesat and find out data from space

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

there was no moment

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

2c. What did you do first?

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

"When something broke or failed, it told me that..."

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

Thank you.

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WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-05	Date completed 29/3/26
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A note before you begin

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Write in whatever way feels natural. Short sentences are fine. You can use bullet points if that helps. The only rule is: write what is true, not what sounds good. If the spaces aren't enough, please use a star mark and write it at the bottom or in an extra sheet.

Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

At first I thought it was just one of [mentor] sir's "impossible" ideas that just pop out of his head
and then never come true BUT... actually when I actually realised that he and [mentor] sir was
serious about this, I was both surprised and concerned about it.

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

Maybe, the main thing it was pursuing was team work.

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

AT first I took this very lightly – I mean imagining a perfectly nice school which is very small
which almost no one knows about, decided to build and launch a SATELLITE???
Immeasurably unbelievable.

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

I really wasn't in the "making the circuit team" – in fact I was in the design team
so, I don't really remember any moment like that.
[* = Same answer (I'm sorry guys)]

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

[* = Same answer (I'm sorry guys)]

2c. What did you do first?

[* = Same answer (I'm sorry guys)]

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

Sorry....

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Would we be ready for this?• How do we understand the sensors in a much deeper way?

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3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

“When something broke or failed, it told me that...”

When something broke or failed, it told me that we have a lot to learn everywhere in life,
to not just succeed but to again learn faithfully until the path to success had a lot of wisdom
and to have that wisdom and succeed, is the greatest thing of all.

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

As for I, I feel confident enough to start afresh about the cubesat and this time
with more teamwork and the same level of knowledge with all of us.

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

Things sure look hard. Either its so big that you become famous or, it's so small that it only affects you.
But just because they look hard doesn't mean they are impossible.
Hard things are possible if you put in ALL your effort otherwise its a waste of time.

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

[* Concerned because I didn't wanna be famous]

Thank you.

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Blue Blocks Micro Research Institute, Hyderabad | March 2026 | Case Study 2 of 5

STUDENT 6 OF 8

BLUE BLOCKS MICRO RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Case Study 2: Innovation and Resilience in Adolescent Learners

WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-06	Date completed April-15
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A note before you begin

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Write in whatever way feels natural. Short sentences are fine. You can use bullet points if that helps. The only rule is: write what is true, not what sounds good. If the spaces aren't enough, please use a star mark and write it at the bottom or in an extra sheet.

Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

When the project began, I was thinking about how we would be able to complete the project because at that time the project seemed quite intimidating.

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

because the prospect of sending a satellite to space sounded very exciting to me

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

When our sensors were not working we were doubtful our project would work at all

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

When our Rocket failed all of us were very upset because we realised we would have
to do everything all over again

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

I thought the rocket had failed and would come crashing back to earth

2c. What did you do first?

hope for better news

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

When the sensors were not working I was quite overwhelmed with the situation

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

We would try to make the satellite more complicated

3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

"When something broke or failed, it told me that..."

We knew that Failure is a step to success

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

We expect to face a lot of challenges along the way
but hopefully we will resolve all of them

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

When you work on something hard you can expect a lot of challenges along the way

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

Thank you.

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STUDENT 7 OF 8

BLUE BLOCKS MICRO RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Case Study 2: Innovation and Resilience in Adolescent Learners

WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-07	Date completed 2/4/26
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A note before you begin

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Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

I thought we were going to build a prototype CubeSat that would only go to the sky and come back

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

because I found that idea very interesting and fun

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

yes at start I questioned myself asking if we would really do this. I felt confused.

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

I couldn't understand what the problem was, but I was sad when I found out that a problem occurred

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

I thought that the sensors had failed to give results

2c. What did you do first?

I asked my teachers what the problem was

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

yes I did think it would not work, and I told myself:
“even if it doesn't work, it's fine, we can restart.”

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

how long will this project take?

3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

“When something broke or failed, it told me that...”

we can start over again.
we need to learn from our mistakes.
we are not perfect at anything.

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

No I don't expect anything to go wrong for now.
Though I think we may have a problem with the origami folds.

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

age doesn't matter, you can achieve anything you want if you work both hard and smart

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

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WEEKEND REFLECTION SHEET

To be completed at home and brought back on Monday.

Name P-08	Date completed
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Set aside about 30 to 40 minutes somewhere quiet. Read each question fully before you start writing.

PART 1

Before it became the project everyone saw

Think back to the very beginning, before any adult helped shape the direction.

1a. What did you personally think you were trying to build or find out?

Not what the project became. What you thought at the start.

We were trying to build a satellite that would not only give us data but become a piece of memorabilia that we were the first teens to build a cubesat

1b. Why that, rather than something else?

What made that question or idea feel worth pursuing to you?

It would prove that we are capable of anything and we wanted to know how it was like in space

1c. Was there a moment early on when you were uncertain whether the project was even possible? What did that feel like?

Yes. it felt like it was impossible for teens to make a satellite.

PART 2

When something went wrong

Do not describe the resolved version. Describe the moment it went wrong.

2a. What happened? Be as specific as you can.

Not 'we had a problem with the sensor.' What exactly happened, and when did you realise it?

When we watched the rocket launch with our satellite everything seemed good... until it failed. I was also happy that we had made it this far

2b. What did you think had happened, right at that moment?

Your first reading of the situation, even if it turned out to be wrong.

I was really sad but I was also happy that we even made it this far

2c. What did you do first?

I was just comforting my friends

2d. Was there a point where you thought it would not work at all? What did you do with that thought?

No

PART 3

What you understand now

3a. What would you ask if you were starting the project again?

Not 'we would do X differently.' What question would you bring to the start that you did not know to ask before?

How do we know it will work

3b. Complete this sentence in as many ways as you want:

"When something broke or failed, it told me that..."

we could do it again

3c. Is there anything you now expect to go wrong when you start something new? Has working on this project changed how you think about that?

No

PART 4

One last thing

Answer whichever of these feels most true. You do not need to answer both.

4a. If you were explaining what you learned from this project to someone who had never built anything, what would you say?

Not what you learned about satellites. What you learned about working on something hard.

Just do it even if you fail at least you tried

4b. Is there anything about the experience that you have not had a chance to say yet, in any debrief or conversation? If so, write it here.

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